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ЖУРНАЛ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ | JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

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THE HISTORY OF THE GERMAN LANGUAGE AND THE EXPRESSION OF WORDS

ANNOTATION

In the article, the history of the German language, opinions and considerations about the umlaut (consonants) of the words in this language are given, and strong umlaut verbs are also given.

Key words: language, German, umlaut, content, development, internal law, history, stage, improvement, vocabulary.

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ИСТОРИЯ НЕМЕЦКОГО ЯЗЫКА И ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ СЛОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье приводится история немецкого языка, мнения и соображения об умлаутах (согласных) слов в этом языке, а также сильные глаголы умлаута.

Ключевые слова: язык, немецкий, умлаут, содержание, развитие, внутреннее право, история, этап, совершенствование, словарный запас.

SAIDALIYEVA Mamura

*Xorijiy tillar kafedrasida o'qituvchisi
Tabiiy Resurslar*

NEMIS TILI TARIXI VA SO'ZLARINING IFODASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada nemis tili tarixi, bu tildagi so'zlarning umlaut (undosh) haqidagi fikr va mulohazalar berilgan, kuchli umlaut fe'llari ham berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, nemis, umlaut, tarkib, rivojlanish, ichki qonun, tarix, bosqich, takomillashtirish, lug'at.

The history of the German language is a linguistic discipline that studies the gradual development and improvement of all components of the German language. The interdependence and interdependence of the language, the search for internal laws of its development, as well as the formation and formation of the language of the German people and nation. The history of a language determines the forms of its existence (oral or written) at certain stages of development, as well as the presence or absence of a supradialectal form [1, B.34].

The history of the German language is a general field of linguistics. He studies and describes phonological system, grammatical structure from the point of view of diachrony vocabulary and stylistic system of the German language. Many phenomena would remain incomprehensible without the history of language. This linguistic discipline reveals the current state of language by analyzing its development. For example: findan - fand - fundum - gifundan helfan-yarim-hulfum-giholfan (See: finden, three main modern forms of the verb helfen). The appearance of different vowels in the root of the verb of indefinite form is explained through the prism of historical development: in the presence of a nasal in the compound. with other consonants, the vowel i appeared in the root, but if the presence of u or o in the final form is treated in the same way [2, B.78].

While studying the history of the language before determining the goals and objectives, it is appropriate to emphasize the role and importance of the history of the language in learning the mother tongue. This role is such that the forms of the native language become intelligible only when their occurrence is observed. and gradual development. It is even more important to observe the interaction between relevant foreign languages, to identify obsolete and dead forms and to distinguish them from production forms [3, B.56].

All this is necessary in learning a foreign language in order to actively master it. Similar familiarity helps develop an intuitive language sense, which in turn leads to learning other languages. Studying the history of the language also creates a basis for a deeper and historically meaningful understanding of the current language.

For example, strong umlaut verbs take the root vowel in the 2nd and the 3rd person singular present tense, often seems to be a strange phenomenon, and how it is memorized is an invariable rule of grammar, can be a historical explanation can: du fährst, er, sie, es fährt, cf. dvn. du ferist, er, sie, es ferit. Umlaut has its roots in the distant past, in Old High German (Dvn.). root vowel a takes umlaut under the influence of i or j, ie. goes to e; similarly: alt - eltiro - eltisto. Familiarity with the history of the language is of great importance not only for practical, but also for theoretical purposes. learning German helps to understand the process of formation of the German vocabulary, grammatical categories, as well as the phonological system.

The internal patterns of the modern German language The language cannot be understood without familiarizing itself with the linguistic patterns of the ancient periods of its development. So, for example, the use of the present tense (now) in the future sense is explained by the fact that it was so in antiquity. there was no contrast of two verbal forms - present - future. Future tense forms appeared much later.

The present tense serves as a temporary form and indicates future action. (In modern German, Präsens is often used in the sense of the future, when there are lexical indicators in the sentence. about the course of future action, for example: morgen, in die ser Voche, etc.). The theoretical importance of studying the history of the German language

The language does not tire of what is said. Acquaintance with it and the history of any other language expands the horizons of the common language, leads to a deeper understanding and a deeper understanding of the laws of language development in general [4, B.90].

Penetration into the mother tongue. The main task of studying the history of language is to analyze the evolutionary changes that have occurred in all linguistic phenomena over the centuries. The history of language studies the internal laws that govern the development of all components of the language: grammatical structure, vocabulary, orthographic features, sound matter (phonetic system).

A consideration of internal patterns shows their historically transitory nature. Known internal laws act in a certain time, but they find their continuation and reflection in the later periods of language development up to the present level. For example, the grammatical alternation of consonants in the root: *schneiden - schnitt - geschnitten* has 10 periods with roots in Old German (compare with Russian: *g - f: run - run; x - w: ear - ear*).

The history of language is considered from the point of view of diachrony. Diachrony refers to the historical development of the entire system as a subject of linguistics study. Synchrony means the state of a language at a certain stage of its historical development. Systems of lexical, grammatical and phonetic elements as a subject of linguistics. These two concepts are important for considering language stability and change. Language change and language stability Any language is a social phenomenon.

This happens at a certain stage of the development of social consciousness and develops under the influence of interaction with a person and society [6B35]. Every language is a dynamic system that is constantly changing, although we may not always notice these changes, for example, changes in the field of phonetics [R] (accepted as a literary standard since 1995); Die Sowjetunion - vibrations in the pronunciation of the first sound [z], [s].

This dynamic is affected by the connection of each specific moment with all the connections of previous history. Language change (*der Sprachwandel*) is by nature a slow evolution. It covers different aspects language is not equal and not at the same pace. In each language, it is possible to observe historical changes occurring in the vocabulary, phonological system, grammatical structure, as well as stylistically existing norms and forms. A dictionary of changes in the world around us most sensitive. Changes happen very quickly in the field of vocabulary.

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